

ANALYSIS OF THEORETICAL APPROACHES AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF TEACHING IN THE FORMATION OF ORAL SPEECH SKILLS IN RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

G.A. Musadjanova¹, F.A. Yakubova²

Senior teacher, Department of Western Languages, Faculty of Philology, Oriental University¹

Senior teacher, Russian Language Department, Tashkent International Kimyo University²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15291194>

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the theoretical and methodological foundations of teaching Russian as a foreign language in the context of the higher education system of Uzbekistan, with a special emphasis on the development of oral communication skills of students. The study examines various theories of language acquisition and pedagogical approaches that can help teachers in choosing effective strategies to improve the level of spoken language proficiency among students. A qualitative approach was used to analyze these theories and methods, aimed at providing insights into the improvement of the learning process. The study emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach, in which the emphasis on grammar skills is complemented by strategies aimed at developing oral communication through authentic, real-life tasks. The conducted research shows that language learning is a dynamic process influenced by linguistic, social, cultural and cognitive factors. It also emphasizes the need for teachers to create an interactive and exciting learning environment that encourages students to participate in authentic communicative situations. Such a student-centered approach, emphasizing cooperation and partnership between teacher and student, is considered necessary for achieving functional language competence. The conclusion formulates recommendations and outlines directions for further research in this area.*

Keywords: *Russian as a foreign language, methodological foundations, oral speech, language acquisition, communicative competence, gaming technologies, linguodidactic model.*

Introduction. The relevance of this work is due to a number of contradictions that hinder the effective development of creative thinking and oral communication skills in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language (RFL) to students with Uzbek as the language of instruction. One of the key contradictions is the gap between modern requirements for specialists working in the international environment, who must have high creativity and developed communication skills, and traditional approaches to teaching a foreign language in universities. These approaches often do not provide sufficient opportunities for active and creative use of the language, which negatively affects the ability of students to develop free oral communication skills [1].

The development of oral communication skills, along with the expansion of vocabulary, is a key criterion for the success of an individual in modern society. The ability to confidently express one's thoughts and communicate effectively in a foreign language is becoming the most important indicator of professional competence, especially in the context of globalization. However, in

practice, there is a discrepancy between students' desire to use creative methods in learning a foreign language, in particular in developing oral speech, and the limited opportunities for their implementation in the university environment [4]. Students want to use the language in real situations, participate in discussions and debates, but existing curricula often focus on grammar and written tasks, which limits the opportunities for active oral communication.

This contradiction is especially evident in the modern educational environment, where high-level proficiency in a foreign language is an important factor in competitiveness in the international labor market [6]. Therefore, to solve this problem, it is necessary to reconsider approaches to teaching RFL, paying more attention to the development of oral speech and creative thinking of students. The introduction of interactive and gaming technologies, as well as the use of situational tasks and trainings can significantly improve the effectiveness of learning, making the language learning process more interesting and motivating for students [7]. Particular attention is paid to the development of oral speech as an integral part of language training, which helps students effectively express their thoughts, participate in discussions and interact with the world around them [10].

According to the state standard of the higher education system of Uzbekistan, the development of oral speech skills and enrichment of students' vocabulary are the most important tasks of the educational process. These tasks contribute to the formation of universal learning activities (ULA), including personal, communicative, regulatory and cognitive components, which together form the basis of the student's competencies [11]. Research by scientists such as L.S. Vygotsky and A.R. Luria demonstrate the importance of vocabulary formation for the development of thinking, which is directly related to oral speech. Expansion of vocabulary is associated with the development of cognitive abilities, including memory and linguistic intuition, which helps students successfully cope with the tasks of communication and cognition of reality [2,3]. The task of enriching vocabulary and developing oral speech is central not only to the subject area of "Russian as a Foreign Language" (RFL), but also to the entire education system. The ability to freely use language tools allows students to reveal their potential in any academic discipline, since all training in universities is based on language [12]. The importance of RFL as a means of intellectual development and the formation of key concepts is emphasized in regulatory documents, such as the state standard of the higher education system of Uzbekistan, which states that the study of RFL should ensure the development of a culture of proficiency in oral and written speech, as well as contribute to the enrichment of students' active and potential vocabulary. One of the key difficulties in developing oral speech and vocabulary is the unsystematic approach to this task. University curricula do not devote enough time to the targeted development of speech skills, and the results of such efforts are often not immediately obvious [14]. To achieve success, student motivation and systematic speech practice are necessary, which requires not only work in the classroom, but also activity outside of class time. In the context of the competence-based approach, which is a priority of the educational system of Uzbekistan, the task of developing oral speech becomes especially relevant. This is confirmed by research in the field of cognitive development and teaching methodology, where emphasis is placed on the importance of the active use of vocabulary and speech for the formation of a full-fledged linguistic personality.

Literature Review. Studying theories of second language acquisition helps to gain a deeper understanding of human thinking and perception of reality. It affects logic, ethics and history in the context of language use. The key question within the theories is whether people think

in language or whether they first think and then translate their thoughts into language [5, 6]. Studying RFL is not limited to communication with native speakers. It helps people get acquainted with the language on a cultural level, which helps to achieve personal goals. Thus, learning a second or new language becomes an accessible and exciting way to understand a new culture through communication with its native speakers [15, 18]. V.N. Wagner argues that in accordance with the selected speech topics and meanings of the utterance, a systematic organization of lexical material is carried out. Due to the complexity, fragmentation and diverse nature, it is impossible to use a single classification criterion. It is methodologically rational to use the following criteria: thematic, logical-semantic and structural-grammatical." [23, p. 60].

Knowledge of the words of a language is necessary in order to express one's thoughts. There is an assumption that grammatical knowledge is more important than vocabulary. However, Falls argued that traditional second language teaching pays too much attention to grammatical structures [19, 20,]. One of the important questions in second language learning is: "How do students learn a second language?" Understanding the process of learning a second language allows us to develop effective pedagogical approaches. N.V. Bogdanova considers vocabulary as part of the mental lexicon stored in long-term memory. The mental lexicon includes not only the meaning of words, but also their phonological, morphological and syntactic information. The author believes that, from the point of view of both teachers and students, it is advisable to classify vocabulary into receptive (vocabulary for perception), productive (vocabulary for active use) and potential (vocabulary for further assimilation) [21, 22,]. One of the problems of learning is the complexity of the Russian lexical system itself, which includes polysemantic words and discrepancies in meanings between Russian and the students' native languages. This complicates the process of semantization and causes errors in the use of words. Russian as a foreign language classes often focus on learning, which is often aimed at passing standardized tests, rather than developing communication skills. As a result, students may know the rules, but cannot effectively use the language in real situations.

According to O.V. Klokova, systematization requires certain techniques to identify information about the meaning of a word, therefore visualization, interpretation of a word, definition of synonyms or antonyms, consideration of context provide an objective description of the material being studied [10, p. 121]. The concept of oral fluency varies depending on the context and can be interpreted in different ways. In most cases, teachers associate fluency with the smoothness and ease of students' speech. Students who have fluent oral speech can demonstrate confident proficiency in the language, but this does not necessarily indicate the accuracy of speech, compliance with grammar rules [23]. Modern research in the field of second language learning emphasizes that successful language acquisition requires a balanced development of both fluency and accuracy of speech.

Methodology. The problem of developing students' oral speech, as well as enriching their vocabulary in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language (RFL) in Uzbekistan is one of the key tasks of the educational system. This task becomes especially relevant in the context of the need to improve the level of language competence and communication skills. This study examines methods and approaches to the development of students' oral speech through systematic work on expanding their vocabulary. Students studying RFL demonstrate different levels of language proficiency, which necessitates individualization of approaches in the educational process. An important factor is the development of not only grammatical skills, but also communicative

abilities that contribute to the successful acquisition of the language and its active use in oral speech. The development of oral speech is closely related to cognitive processes such as thinking, memory and perception. Among first-year bachelor's students, there is an increase in cognitive activity, which stimulates the development of oral speech. The expansion of vocabulary during this period is due to the need for self-expression, communicative activity and interaction with the outside world.

L.V. Nikonova notes that complex relationships with people around them during this period stimulate not only the active acquisition of new words, but also the awareness of the wealth of metaphors and phraseological units, which makes oral speech more expressive and rich [7]. However, one of the challenges in teaching students RFL in Uzbekistan is the influence of colloquial and Internet vocabulary, including slang and obscene expressions, which can negatively affect the quality of students' oral speech. This requires teachers to pay special attention to the selection of lexical material, as well as the development of methods that will contribute to the development of language culture and the correct use of the Russian language in oral speech [9]. The use of gaming technologies in the process of teaching RFL is one of the effective approaches to enriching vocabulary and developing oral speech. Gaming activities help students master new material in a relaxed atmosphere, maintaining their interest in learning.

Games stimulate creativity, active participation in the learning process, which contributes to better memorization of words and the development of oral speech skills. In the game, students have the opportunity to interact with each other, try themselves in various communicative roles, which increases their motivation and interest in the language material. Based on my own experience of working with students, I can conclude that the use of modern pedagogical technologies, such as game forms of learning and interactive tasks, contributes to the effective development of students' oral speech. Such methods allow creating favorable conditions for language practice, while activating the cognitive processes that are necessary for the acquisition and active use of new vocabulary. To solve the problem of developing students' oral speech and enriching their vocabulary, educational materials on Russian as a foreign language should be specially adapted. A special role in this is played by tasks aimed at working with little-known words and phraseological units, which not only helps expand the vocabulary, but also makes students' speech richer and more expressive.

Results. An important aspect in the teaching process is not only increasing the volume of vocabulary, but also its active use in speech activity, which is especially important in the context of oral speech development. To successfully complete this task, it is necessary to take into account the psychophysiological characteristics of students' speech development and the specifics of learning new vocabulary in conjunction with cognitive processes. The process of mastering a language and, in particular, its lexical component occurs in the context of communication and interaction with the outside world. In the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language, three types of vocabulary are distinguished: active, passive and potential.

- Active vocabulary includes words that the student not only understands, but also uses in his or her oral speech. This is the main resource through which communication and the creation of coherent statements occur.

- Passive vocabulary includes words that the student understands, but does not use in his or her speech. Despite this, passive vocabulary plays an important role in the perception of speech and the expansion of students' speech experience.

- Potential vocabulary consists of words that the student has not encountered before, but can guess their meaning based on context, intuition, and knowledge of typical word formation patterns.

Each of these types of vocabulary is closely related to the development of oral speech skills. One of the main tasks of the teacher is to transfer as many words as possible from the passive and potential vocabulary to the active one, so that students can use them in oral speech.

1. Communicatively significant errors. These errors change the meaning of a phrase or the entire text, leading to an incorrect interpretation of information and increasing misunderstanding between the interlocutors. They can significantly hinder the development of oral speech and prevent the active use of new words in context. Elimination of such errors requires both improving pronunciation and careful study of lexical units, which contributes to a more accurate expression of thoughts.

2. Communicatively insignificant errors. These errors do not seriously affect the overall meaning of communication, but their correction is still necessary to improve the level of language proficiency and enrich the vocabulary of students. Even minor errors can limit students in more complex forms of communication and reduce confidence in using new vocabulary. To solve these problems, it is important not only to correctly select teaching methods aimed at eliminating errors, but also strategies that support the expansion of vocabulary and its active use in oral speech.

The authors of the article propose the following methods for solving these problems, which contribute to both the development of oral speech and the increase in active vocabulary:

1. The “Text-oriented approach to expanding vocabulary” method in teaching Russian as a foreign language. The use of authentic texts that correspond to the language level of students is much more effective than traditional distribution or compilation of lists of words for memorization. Texts provide an opportunity to see words in a natural context, which helps students better understand their meaning and scope of use.

2. The “Listening with repetition” method. This method involves not only listening to texts, but also actively repeating after the speaker. By repeating new words and phrases, students learn their pronunciation and memorize their meanings, which helps integrate these words into their active vocabulary.

3. The method of “Listening with simultaneous pronunciation”. Combining listening and pronunciation helps students not only develop oral speech, but also consolidate new words in active memory. Simultaneous speaking stimulates speech activity, which allows for faster integration of new lexical elements into everyday speech.

4. The method of “Listening with visual support”. Including printed texts or texts on the screen gives students the opportunity to associate the sound and spelling of words, which makes it easier to memorize and actively use them. This technique is especially useful for working with new vocabulary, since visual supports help to better learn and consolidate new words.

5. Game technologies. Game technologies, widely used in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language, are an effective tool for enriching the vocabulary and activating students' speech activity. The game as a form of educational activity actively contributes to the development of students' cognitive and communicative abilities.

Conclusion. The use of gaming technologies plays an important role in the development of various educational and universal educational activities (ULA) in students, contributing to the comprehensive formation of their skills. In particular, gaming approaches effectively support the

development of personal competencies, helping students to form value guidelines and a meaningful focus in learning. Regulatory skills, such as organizing their own educational activities, are also successfully developed through gaming tasks, which helps to increase students' independence and responsibility. Cognitive skills associated with the ability to work with information, and communicative competencies, implying the ability to interact with others, are also significantly developed through such technologies. Particular attention in gaming exercises is paid to the development of oral speech and active vocabulary of students.

To enrich vocabulary, methods aimed at working through rare and obsolete words, such as borrowings, archaisms and folklore, are actively used. The use of context, as well as familiar meanings of polysemantic words and typical morphemes, contributes to better acquisition and activation of potential vocabulary. It is important that work on the development of oral speech and expansion of vocabulary can be continued and integrated into other educational processes. The use of game technologies for the development of students' speech and communication skills opens up new opportunities for teachers who can use them when teaching not only Russian, but also other school subjects. The development of these competencies, especially oral speech skills, remains a pressing task within the framework of educational activities, which requires further research and the introduction of modern pedagogical resources.

REFERENCES

1. Артеменко Н.А. Обогащение словарного запаса учащихся с опорой на идеографический подход // Научно-педагогическое обозрение. 2014. С. 53–59.
2. Выготский Л. С. Мышление и речь. М.: Лабиринт, 1999. 352 с.
3. Лурия А. Р. Язык и сознание. СПб.: Питер, 2020. 448 с.
4. Эльконин Д. Б. Развитие речи в дошкольном возрасте. М.: Изд-во Акад. пед. наук РСФСР, 1958. 116 с.
5. Глухов В. П. Основы психолингвистики: учебное пособие для студентов педвузов. М.: АСТ: Астрель, 2005. 351 с.
6. Корнеева Т. А. К вопросу о развитии словарного запаса учащихся на уроках русского языка // Филология и наука. 2016. № 3 (45). С. 184–189.
7. Никонова Л. В. Развитие лексикона детей младшего подросткового возраста // Образование и наука. 2013. № 4. С. 144–160.
8. Богачева И.В., Откидач Н.А., Борисова Л.П. Организация работы по обогащению словарного запаса учащихся как аспекта языкового образования на уроках русского языка в средней школе // Современный ученый. 2020. № 4. С. 28–34.
9. Леонтьев А. Н. Психологические основы дошкольной игры // Психологическая наука и образование. 1996. № 3. С. 19–31.
10. Клокова О.В. Особенности изучения и преподавания лексики на занятиях по русскому языку // Язык, культура и профессиональная коммуникация в современном обществе: Материалы VIII Международной научной конференции. Отв. ред. О.А. Дронова. – 2019. – С. 119–123
11. Михайленко Т. М. Игровые технологии как вид педагогических технологий // Педагогика: традиции и инновации: материалы Междунар. науч. конф. Челябинск: Два комсомольца, 2011. Т. 1. С. 140–146.

12. Емельянова О. Н. О «пассивном словарном запасе языка» и «устаревшей лексике» // Русская речь. 2004. № 1. С. 46–50.
13. Бессонова М. С. Обогащение словарного запаса на уроках русского языка в младших классах // Вестник Адыгейского государственного университета. Серия 3: Педагогика и психология. 2010. № 3. С. 90–94.
14. Горина О. Г. Определение словарного запаса обучаемых с помощью корпуса // Вестник Ленинградского государственного университета им. А. С. Пушкина. 2013. № 2. С. 201–209.
15. Микерова Г. Г., Павленко А. А. Развитие уровня активного словарного запаса младших школьников // Символ науки. 2017. № 1. С. 203–207.
16. Хардинг Ж. Когда не хватает слов: почему важно расширять словарный запас // Вестник Воронежского государственного университета. Серия: Лингвистика и межкультурная коммуникация. 2017. № 3. С. 138–141.
17. Забусова Е. И. Пополнение словаря учащихся на уроках литературного чтения и русского языка // Символ науки. 2019. № 11. С. 97–99.
18. Ярославцева Н. В., Беляков А. А., Тухватуллин Б. Т., Кодоева А. Ч., Нигаматулин В. Р., Левченко Д. В., Дахин А. Н. Когнитивная технология обучения: сущность, эффективность и результативность // Перспективы науки и образования. 2020. № 1 (43). С. 10–23. DOI: 10.32744/pse.2020.1.1
19. Богдан С. С., Лашкова Л. Л., Лукиянчина Е. В. Формирование критического мышления на основе универсальных когнитивных установок, стратегий и инструментов // Science for Education Today. 2019. Т. 9, № 2. С. 37–51. DOI: 10.15293/2658-6762.1902.03
20. Киндря Н.А. Лексический аспект в обучении русскому языку как иностранному // Мир науки, культуры, образования. 2018. № 3 (70). С. 44–46.
21. Фолс, К. (2004). Мифы о лексике: применение изучения второго языка в преподавании в классе. Энн-Арбор, Мичиган: Издательство Мичиганского университета.
22. Н.В. Богданова Методика обучения иностранному языку в работе над словарным запасом в тандем-группах. Научно-технические ведомости СПбГПУ. Гуманитарные и общественные науки. (239) 2016
23. Вагнер В.Н. Лексика русского языка как иностранного и ее преподавание: учеб. пособие. – 2-е изд. – М.: Флинта: Наука, 2009. – 104 с.
24. Хотамовна, М. Ф. (2024). PROBLEMS IN SYNCHRONIC TRANSLATION IN THE DIGITAL AGE AND THEIR SOLUTIONS: PROMOTING VR TECH LABS FOR SYNCHRONIC TRANSLATION. *IMRAS*, 7(7), 203-205.